

23.09.2025 / IEA Task 52 meeting 2025

Measuring Offshore Wakes with Nacelle-Scanning Lidars: New Scan Strategy and Key Insights

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Why install scanning lidars on a nacelle?

Offshore wake measurement!

Blockage + misalignment of wind direction to the scan pattern !

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Campaign C^2 -Wakes

Goal of the campaign

- Wake control study
- Near and far wake of a single wind farm
- Wake superposition for two different turbine technologies

German north sea, adjacent with four wind farms

- 3 scanning lidars
- deployed on turbine nacelles
- Measurement range around 12 km
- 90° plan position indicator (PPI) scans
- 90 s per scan

Challenge

Nacelle installation

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- Moving coordinate system
- Scanning lidar v.s. scanning lidar at various ranges

Ground installation

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- Static, onshore environment
- Scanning lidar v.s. (cups or profiling lidars or scanning lidars)

To Summarize, you need

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Orientation

1 Hz GNSS antenna measurement

Different quality in GNSS measurement

Azimuth-wise offsets later found via hard-target fitting

Motion sensor set

Complexity of motion mode

During installation....

Typical day

Line-of-sight wind speed

Scan geometry

Scan geometry and comparison domain

axis	resolution
X	75m
Y	150m
Z	10m

Two independent moving coordinates system → static common grid

Comparison methodology

Result: regression

30-minute average interval, @ hub height

- Total 1014 samples
- Samples of A80 alone = 3517
- Samples of A70 alone = 1066
- RMSE (root mean square error) = 0.7115 m/s
- MBE (mean bias error) = 0.1653 m/s

Result: bin standard error 30-minute average interval , @ hub height

- In the order of 0.65 m/s for projected wind speed above 8 m/s
- Highest standard error : 1.11 m/s

Key advantages

- minimal blockage
- small angle difference with the main wind direction

Limitations & Uncertainty Sources

- co-locality & motion compensation
- turbulence : ambient turbulence and wake-induced turbulence
- interpolation errors

Take away

This research was conducted under the C²-Wakes project (ref. no. 03EE3087A), funded by the Federal Minister for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWE) based on a decision by the German Bundestag.

We express our sincere gratitude to all team members involved in the campaign. Special thanks to Stephan Stone, Christian Tietjen, Asif Abdullah (Fraunhofer Institute for Wind Energy Systems IWES), Jörg Schneemann, Janna Seifert, Daniel Ribnitzky, Timo Brunssen (ForWind - Center for Wind Energy Research University of Oldenburg), Justin Burstein, Frauke Theuer, Mona Morgenstern, Claus Linnemann (RWE Offshore Wind) for their dedication in carrying out the field work, coordination, or monitoring tasks. Your collaborative efforts have been invaluable to the project. We also extend our appreciation to RWE, the operator of the Amrumbank West offshore wind farm, for enabling and supporting the lidar measurement campaign.

Thank you
for your time!

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